

MULTI-AXIAL WARP KNITTED LAYERS - A TEXTILE FOR REINFORCING CONCRETE

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SUMMARY: The aims described before will be achieved by presenting the historical propagation in civil engineering from asbestos to glass fibres respectively alkaline resistant glass fibres. A short summary of existing technologies for processing short fibres with concrete matrices will show today's state of the art. Both aspects will be compared with the historical development of fibre reinforced plastics technologies. Derived from this comparison the necessary technology transfer from plastics to concretes will be obvious. Following this idea it will be presented how a new composite material has been born by reinforcing concrete with textiles. The results of a project including production of multiaxial layer fabrics, matrix optimization, production of test specimen and determination of mechanical properties will prove the technical and economical qualification of the new composite material in comparison with short fibre reinforcement.

KEYWORDS: textile reinforced concrete, alkali-resistant glass fibre, fibre tests, warp knitted multi-axial layer fabric WIMAG, stitch-bonded variable layer fabric NVG,

INTRODUCTION

The reinforcement of mineral matrix systems using fibres has long been a state-of-the-art technique. The best known and quantitatively most widespread are asbestos fibres and building components reinforced with these. The need to find a substitute for asbestos fibres worldwide resulted in a shift of interest to, among other substances, glass fibres. In order to use these in a concrete matrix it was essential that the fibres be resistant to the alkaline environment if they were to retain their very good mechanical qualities for a sufficient duration. The development, 25 years ago, of alkali-resistant glass fibres enabled glass fibres in the form of short strands to be used for reinforcing concrete matrices, a technique which has become firmly established in the construction sector and is applied in a wide variety of ways. Some improvement is needed if optimal advantage is to be taken of these fibres, particularly in view of the short length of the fibres and the fact that their orientation is not always appropriate for achieving the bearing capacity required. The effectiveness of the fibres is to be improved by using glass filament yarns and orienting them in accordance with the function of the particular building component in

question. A technological variant is the production of textile fabrics that meet these requirements. At present knitting technology with its variable stitch-bonding techniques is ideal for the manufacture of such structures. Initial tests have been carried out at the Institute for Textiles and Clothing Technology, TU Dresden, and at the Institute for Textile Technology, RWTH Aachen, as a part of AiF project no. 9272/B [1]. The results of these tests form the basis for this talk.

FIBRE TESTS

Reinforcement materials in a concrete building component are subject to media influences right from the start of the manufacturing process until the end of their service life. These include the alkaline influence from the concrete matrix and the acidic influence of rainwater seepage at defective points. In Germany, very high demands have to be met proving the durability of new building materials before their introduction in the construction industry. Tests concerning the influence of the above-mentioned media on the qualities of the reinforcement materials are therefore of particular interest.

This research project made use of the special glass fibres NEG AR H-340V, 650 tex produced by Nippon Electric Glass. These fibres have a raised zirconium content (ZrO_2), providing good resistance in fine concrete. These fibres are referred to as alkali-resistant (AR) glass fibres. The yarns produced by Nippon Electric Glass are the only such fibres suited treatment as textiles and they were selected for these tests for this reason [1,2].

The experiments testing resistance to artificial rainwater (pH 6) and to sodium hydroxide (pH 12,1), which corresponds to the pH value of a special concrete matrix, were conducted according to the established norms. The fibre material was taken from a spool and laid out in test groups in developing trays which were subsequently filled with the solutions. The trays were then covered to prevent evaporation, thus ensuring constant pH values.

The test materials were then stored in a climatic chamber. After 24 hours, 7 days and 28 days they were removed, air-dried for three hours and then subjected to bending pressure. The force: bending ratio was determined in accordance with bending pressure test DIN 53834, part 1. Figure 1 shows the specific tensile strength of the AR glass fibre yarns in relation to duration of storage and the medium applied.

The results show that with the specimens stored in normal climate conditions only minor changes in durability are recorded, so that comparisons can be made between these and the specimens exposed to the special conditions as described above. After drying, the samples stored in the solutions have a slightly adhesive structure. The fibre lengths stored in rainwater, in particular, lead to higher degrees of durability as a result of these adhesive qualities which have the effect of bonding fibre and matrix together.

Fig. 1: Specific tensile strength of AR glass filament yarns under the influence of media and duration of exposure

The fibre lengths stored in sodium hydroxide solution show only minor changes in durability, thus confirming their good resistance to alkaline media.

PRODUCTION OF MULTI-AXIAL LAYER FABRICS FOR REINFORCEMENT OF CONCRETE

Two multi-axial types of textiles will be manufactured for the initial basic tests on the suitability of long-fibre from AR-glass reinforcements in concrete matrices. The two manufacturing techniques which will be compared are MALIMO stitch bonding, with the stitch-bonded variable layer fabric (NVG) manufactured applying this technique, and the LIBA technique, together with its product, the warp knitted multi-axial layer fabric (WIMAG).

Production Of Warp Knitted-Multi-Axial Layer Fabrics (Wimag)

The warp knitted multi-axial layer fabrics are used successfully in the field of plastic composites technology. This is due to the cost-effective production and excellent mechanical properties of WIMAG. Depending on the size of the machine, the textile (cf. Fig. 2) may comprise up to 8 layers of fibres and an additional 2 covering layers of fibre mats, which are fixed in place by warp knitted mesh threads.

Fig. 2 also illustrates the warp knitting machine (LIBA system) with its four weft insertion systems, as has been used at the Department of Textile technology of the Technical University of Aachen (ITA) for manufacturing WIMAG.

Fig. 2: Warp Knitted Multi-Axial Layer Fabrics (LIBA-Technique)

Here the reinforcing threads (2) are drawn off the warping creel (1) and inserted by the weft inserting systems in the required directions. The weft inserting systems oscillate between the needle transport chains (3), which fix the deposited fibres to the machine during transportation.

The weft inserting systems can be mounted in a fixed position (90°) or variably (30° to 60°) or (-30° to -60°) to the direction of production. 0° threads can be fed directly from warp beams (6). It is also possible to supply non-woven fabrics or fibre mats as covering layers via rollers (5).

The warp knitted multi-axial layer fabric, designed in this manner, is fixed in place in the knitting unit (8). The warp knitting threads are removed from the warp beams (7). The finished WIMAG (9) is wound on at the end onto a cloth beam (10).

PRODUCTION OF STITCH-BONDED VARIABLE LAYER FABRICS (NVG)

During the manufacture of stitch-bonded materials (cf. Fig. 3), a parallel weft yarn sheet is first of all laid with the aid of a weft guiding carriage. The continuous advance feed of the transport chain during laying causes this yarn sheet to be inserted at an angle of about 88° , and not precisely at 90° .

Using two variable thread guiding systems (V1 and V2), parallel yarn sheets can be inserted at an angle of between 0° and about 80° , and in addition, the distance between the threads can be altered. This allows the reinforcing textile to be reinforced locally in certain zones, which lie within the subsequent building component, for example in the zones where force is applied.

The weft thread sheet is fed to the knitting elements, together with the other thread layers. The reinforcing threads are fixed in place with the aid of a sewing yarn system which creates knitted meshes. Thus, this procedure combines elements of sewing (passing through and combining thread layers) and of knitting (creating knitted meshes from a large number of individual threads at the same time).

Fig. 3: Malimo stitch-bonding technique

The Malimo stitch-bonding technique is applied at the Institute of Textile and clothing Technology at the Technical University of Dresden (ITB).

TESTS ON THE TEXTILE PROPERTIES OF THE REINFORCEMENT

The physical tests show that the processing of the reinforcement fibres into a net-shaped structure has been done satisfactorily, although the meshes sometimes have rather irregular thread patterns. With 90° oriented rovings the WIMAG fabrics were found to have somewhat better properties than the NVG fabrics (cf. Fig. 4). With 45° orientation hardly any difference was found in the test values for the two types of fabric [2].

Fig. 4: Comparison of maximum tensile strength of the reinforcement textiles

Since working with these substances as textiles is not without its difficulties, the fabrics achieve a yarn strength of only 43% (as cited by the Manufacturer). Causes of this include the slightly wavy formation of yarn resulting from the open structure and from defects in the material used.

THE COMPOSITE ELEMENTS

Three different net-shaped structures (S1, S2, S3) with 90° and +/- 45° oriented reinforcing fibres, made from AR fibre glass, is manufactured from the two types of textiles described above; the different fabric types can be compared. Net-shaped structures have been selected in order to ensure that the textile is impregnated by the relatively high viscous concrete.

A special-purpose matrix material has been developed on the basis of experience derived using types of short-staple reinforced concrete; this material attacks fibre glass less by forming a medium which is less alkaline around the fibre glass. These cement matrices are based on Portland cement with highly efficient alkali binding components. This type of cement was therefore selected for trials with the following additives (weights), on the recommendation of industry [3]:

Cement	1	part
Sand	1	part
Water	0,42 to 0,48	parts
Liquefier	0,22 to 0,04	parts
LP 1-87 Addiment	0,003	parts

THE PRODUCTION OF THE TEST SPECIMENS

The test pieces are manufactured with aid of a positioning unit which allows the reinforcing textiles to be guided into the mould tool in a defined manner (cf. Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Production of Test Specimens

The divisible mould tools are fixed in place above the positioning rods. Once the bottom halves of the mould tools have been positioned and filled, the reinforcing composite is fixed in place with the aid of clamping elements. The tension applied merely serves to ensure that the textile is laid evenly; in other words, no elastic deformation of the reinforcing textile is generated.

Once the composite has been fixed in place, the top and bottom of the mould tool are screwed together and filled with concrete. The complete mould tool can now be raised from the positioning unit and placed in a climatic chamber to be stored for 28 days.

RESULTS OF THE MECHANICAL TESTS

The first series of tests, in which the two more open glass structures were tested, proves that the concrete with 0.42 parts by weight of water and 0,035 parts by weight of cement liquefier can withstand the highest maximum bending pressure. The specimens were tested after only 10 days curing time. At this stage the composite material still does not possess its ultimate properties. Nevertheless, the calculated bending tensions should only be viewed initially for the purpose of comparison in order to determine the ideal make-up of the concrete. In this series of trials, the concrete samples with the WIMAG glass reinforcing of greater density possess a maximum bending strength of 9.1 N/mm², as opposed to 5.08 N/mm² in the case of non-reinforced concrete.

The optimised aggregate parts were used in the actual final of trials. The test pieces, which were produced applying the same process, were now stored for 28 days. The results of 4-point bending test are illustrated in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Results of the 4-Point-Bending Test

It is clear that the modulus of rupture (MOR) of the textile reinforced concrete specimens (21.0 N/mm²) is up to four times higher than of non-reinforced concrete (5.1 N/mm²). This maximum value was achieved using the WIMAG AR glass structures of greatest density (WGS3). The more open (S2 or S1) or NVG structures lie somewhat below the maximum values.

THE PRODUCTION OF A DEMONSTRATOR COMPONENT

For demonstration purposes, a girder used a window lintel, geometrically measuring 700 mm x 140 mm x 140 mm. In order to minimise its weight, the building component is built as a hollow concrete profile with a styrodur core measuring 700 mm x 100 mm x 100 mm. The girders were made by the Institute of Supporting Frameworks and Building Materials at the Technical University of Dresden, using the optimised concrete composition and with the aid of double moulds (cf. Fig. 7).

Fig. 7: Production of a Window Lintel

The reinforcing structures are first impregnated separately with the concrete matrix in a tray, before then being inserted in the mould and evenly aligned with a 2 kg weight at either end. The matrix material is fed into the bottom of the mould, and the styrodur core is then inserted; it is centred using U-shaped spacer pieces at either end of the mould. The remaining hollow spaces are then filled, and air pockets are removed by compressing the matrix. After curing, the girders are removed from the mould, impregnated in the water bath and stored for 28 days at climatic conditions of 20 °C and 55 % relative humidity.

Following the storage of the window lintels, the sides which were facing up during manufacture are ground. The girders are then tested in 4-point bending tests, conforming to DIN 51300 and DIN 51302. The breaking load, deformation and extension of the girders are ascertained.

The suitability of the different types of composites for reinforcing concrete building components can be judged taking the modulus of rupture (MOR) as an example (cf. Fig. 8). It clearly has a greater bearing capacity than concrete which is either non-reinforced or else only reinforced using chopped strands. The extension and deformation values of the reinforced windows lintels are also calculated as being clearly higher than the comparable values for the girders which were either non-reinforced or else only short-staple reinforced. The final appraisal of the results of the trials will have to be carried out following completion of the final trials [4].

Fig. 8: Results of the Mechanical Testing of the Demonstrator Components

CONCLUSION AND PROGNOSIS

The results of this research project show that sheets made up of AR glass fibre threads applied as reinforcements for concrete components can lead to better use of materials and hence reduce costs. A proportion of glass amounting to 1% by volume applied in this way produces the same durability as a 3-5% proportion applied as short-staple glass fibres. By orienting the yarns in accordance with the demand to be placed on the building component in question, a higher degree of efficiency is achieved in the reinforcement material. The results also show however, that there is still more room for improvement in the properties of the fabric sheets as regards their ability to be treated as textiles. Improvements in this sphere would lead to further enhancement of the properties of building components with respect to durability and the minimisation of weight.

More highly developed alkali-resistant glass filament yarns are currently being tested by Nippon Electric Glass with regard to their textile properties and as reinforcement materials for very thin concrete elements. In the future it is intended to establish rules on the dimensions of reinforcing sheets made of alkali-resistant glass fibre threads.

In order to solve the problems regarding the textile properties of these products, such as improvement of their processing potential, enhancement of fibre/matrix adhesion, and development of reinforcement structures appropriate to loading and processing demands, it is essential that there be intensive cooperation between manufacturers of fibres, textile machine

producers, the textile industry, and research institutions, always bearing in mind, of course, the needs of the end consumer, the construction industry.

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